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Non-Availability and Integration of ICT Devices in Literacy Centres: Implication to Adult Learning in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The study investigated non-availability and integration of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti state. Specifically, the study examined the level of availability and extent of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State; and the challenges faced using this ICT tools for learning in the literacy class. The descriptive research of the survey type was adopted in this study. The population consisted of all adults who are students in literacy centres in Ekiti state. The sample for this study consisted of 90 adults who are students in literacy centres in Ekiti state. The sample was selected using purposive sampling techniques. ICT Devices Questionnaire (ICTDQ) was used to collect relevant data for the study. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions. The findings of this study revealed that that level of availability and extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State were low. The challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class are inadequate ICT devices; irregular electricity hampering the utilization of available ICT tools for learning; lack of ready access to internet; lack of required technical support; and shortage of facilitators in the appropriate use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning process in the literacy centre. It was recommended among others that Government should equip adult literacy centres with adequate ICT devices. Also Facilitators of adult programme should endeavour to incorporate and prioritise the use of ICT in teaching

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and learning process.

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Introduction

Adult education is the group of schooling activities available for people who for diverse reasons did not study or who dropped out early. The aim is to provide people with opportunities to overcome their living conditions by enhancing different practical skills that can be used in the work place or in future life experiences. Adult education is expected to address the socio-economic, cultural, political and environmental problems besieging humanity in their various societies. This is so because adults are the major occupants of the production sectors of the economy. In spite of the global recognition of the importance of adult education to both individual and the nation at large, a substantial number of people are still illiterate. Some lack literacy skills because they have not had the opportunity or the means to attend school and some others because their schooling was cut short or was of poor quality.

The use of computers in education have ended up as a significant instrument and innovatively affected how we learn and see the world in broad. Today, the place of ICTs in education cannot be quantified. Modern instructional techniques required the use of ICT which provide a more simplified and reliable teaching and learning methodologies. Students can adjust their learning paces with immediate feedback and self-assessment in an institution where the new technologies are being used. Such students extend their learning capabilities beyond classrooms as they can communicate with peers from everywhere around the globe.

Onyekwe (2006) saw ICT as a broad based electronic technology that is used for collecting, storing, processing and transmitting information in various forms. ICT is, therefore, technology that generally supports the individual's ability to manage and communicate information electronically. Thus, for adults not to be left out in what is happening in the world, they to key in into the use and application of this technology and this can only be achieved through the integration of ICT into adult education in Nigeria.

The advent and increasing availability of information and communication technologies (ICTs) have impacted meaningfully in every sphere of human endeavour and have significantly changed the practices and processes of virtually all forms of activities as people now have better access to information far ever than before (Dighe, 2008). The adoption of ICT in adult education has a multiplier effect especially in the area of enhancing learning process. It provides learners with a new set of skills which make them globally competitive.

ICTs foster the acquisition and easy absorption of information that gives adult learners the unparalleled prospects to expand their educational pursuit. Empirical evidence has shown that ICT is of immeasurable value to literacy as it constitutes a vibrant force for widening adult learners' access and participation in literacy programmes, facilitate a flexible learning in terms of time and distance and ultimately serve as an indispensable instrument for a lifelong learning process (Jimoyiannis & Gravani, 2011).

The compelling usage of ICT in instruction and learning relies on upon the accessibility of these facilities and the educators' capability in utilizing them. Observation has shown that there are limited functional ICT facilities in most adult literacy centers especially those in the rural areas. This in turn hinders the urge to use them by the adult learners for learning. Also lack of adequate computer literate from the site of instructors, sporadic power supply and insufficient financial support seem to be another set of deterrent militating against successful usage of ICT facilities and resources in adult literacy centers.

The integration of ICT in adult education may face various challenges with respect to policy, planning, infrastructure, learning content and language, capacity-building and financing (Fasakun, 2006). ICT – enhanced adult education requires clearly stated objectives for mobilization of resources and political commitment of the concerned bodies (Igbo, 2008). With respect to challenges of capacity building, some adult educators lack professional training facilities for them to be ICT skilled and computer literate. In fact, one impeding factor of ICT integration in adult education is the skill gap of the people implementing it (Nnazor, 2005). Another great challenge is that financing ICT in adult education programmes requires large capital investment.

The researcher observed that most adult education centres are not equipped with ICT gadgets and tools, computers, internet facilities, assistive technologies like Braille for the virtually improved, mobile wheel chairs for the handicapped adults, among others as a result of huge capital involved. In view of the above, the study investigated non-availability and integration of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti state. The study specifically examined:

- 1) the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State;
- 2) how often Adult Educators utilize the available ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State; and
- 3) the challenges faced using this ICT tools for learning in the literacy class.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised for this study

- 1) What is the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres?
- 2) How often do the Adult Educators utilize the available ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State?
- 3) What are the challenges faced using this ICT tools for learning in the literacy class?

Research Method

The descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted in the study. The design was considered appropriate because this approach allows information to be obtained from a representative sample of the population in the actual situation as they exist. A survey research studies a small sample from a large population from where inferences would be drawn about the characteristics of the defined population.

The population consisted of all adults who are students in literacy centres in Ekiti state. The sample for this study consisted of 90 adults who are students in literacy centres in Ekiti state. The sample was selected using purposive sampling techniques.

The study made use of structured questionnaire titled “ICT Devices Questionnaire (ICTDQ)” which was divided into three sections. Section A of the questionnaire captured the demographic characteristics of respondents; section B consisted of 30 items on the availability and extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres while section C consisted of 10 items on the challenges faced using this ICT tools for learning in the literacy class.

The face and content validity was ascertained by giving the designed questionnaire to experts of Tests and Measurement for vetting before distributing it to the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the test-retest method. A trial test was carried out outside the sampled area. The instrument was administered on ten respondents while the

data collected on the two tests were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation statistics which yielded a co-efficient of 0.75

The researcher personally administered the instrument in each of the institution sampled in the study. The researcher was responsible for the administration and collection of the instrument from the respondents. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, simple percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres?

Frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation score were used to illustrate the responses to items 1 – 30 in section B of ICTDQ. To determine the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres (low, moderate and high), the mean score and standard deviation of the responses were used. The low level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean score ($44.63 - 2.17 = 42.46$). The moderate level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by the mean score (44.63) while the high level of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by adding the mean score and standard deviation ($44.63 + 2.17 = 46.80$). Therefore, low level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres starts from 30.00 to 42.46, the moderate level starts from 42.47 to 46.79 and the high level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres is from 46.80 to 60.00. The level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State is presented in table 1 and figure i.

Table 1: Level of Availability of ICT devices in literacy centres

Levels of availability	No of Respondents	Percentage
Low (30.00 – 42.46)	52	57.78
Moderate (42.47 – 46.79)	24	26.67
High (46.80 – 60.00)	14	15.56
Total	90	100

Table 1 revealed the levels of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State. The result showed that out of 90 respondents, 52 representing 57.78% agreed that there is low level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres. Respondents who agreed that availability of ICT devices in literacy centres is at moderate level were 24 respondents representing 26.67% while only 14 respondents representing 15.56% agreed that availability of ICT devices in literacy centres is high. This showed that the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State was low. Figure i further revealed the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres.

Figure i: Level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State

Research Question 2: How often do the Adult Educators utilize the available ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State?

Frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation score were used to illustrate the responses to items 1 – 30 in section B under extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State. To determine the extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State (low, moderate and high), the mean score and standard deviation of the responses were used. The low extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean score ($68.42 - 5.53 = 62.89$). The moderate extent of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by the mean score (68.42) while the high extent of ICT devices in literacy centres was determined by adding the mean score and standard deviation ($68.42 + 5.53 = 73.95$). Therefore, low extent of ICT devices in literacy centres starts from 30.00 to 62.89, the moderate level starts from 62.90 to 73.94 and the high extent of ICT devices in literacy centres is from 73.95 to 90.00. The extent of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State is presented in table 2 and figure ii.

Table 2: Extent of Utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State

Extents of Utilization	No of Respondents	Percentage
Low (30.00 – 62.89)	49	54.44
Moderate (62.90 – 73.94)	32	35.56
High (73.95 – 90.00)	9	10.00
Total	90	100

Table 2 revealed the extents of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State. The result showed that out of 90 respondents, 49 respondents representing 54.44% had low

extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres. Respondents who agreed that utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres is at moderate extent were 32 respondents representing 35.56% while only 9 respondents representing 10.00% agreed that utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres is high. This showed that the extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State was low. Figure ii further revealed the extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres.

Figure ii: Bar Chart showing extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres

Research Question 3: What are the challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class?

Table 3: Descriptive analysis of challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class

S/N	Items	N	Mean	S.D.	Remark
1	Inadequate ICT devices	90	3.42	0.61	Accepted
2	Irregular electricity hampering the utilization of available ICT tools for learning	90	3.11	0.63	Accepted
3	Lack of ready access to internet	90	2.85	0.69	Accepted
4	The use of ICT tools in the literacy class consumes time more than traditional method	90	2.19	0.75	Rejected
5	Lack of required technical support	90	2.99	0.65	Accepted
6	Shortage of facilitators in the appropriate use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning process in the literacy centre	90	3.17	0.59	Accepted
7	Lack of adequate training of staff on computer usage		2.43	0.78	Rejected

Mean Cut-off: 2.50

Table 3 revealed the challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class. The table revealed that item 4 and 7 with mean mark of 2.19 and 2.43 respectively were rejected because it is less than the mean cut-off of 2.50. It can be concluded that the challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class are: inadequate ICT devices; irregular electricity hampering the utilization of available ICT tools for learning; lack of ready access to internet; lack of required technical support; and shortage of facilitators in the appropriate use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning process in the literacy centre.

Discussion

The result of this study also showed that the level of availability of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State was low. This implies that ICT devices were not adequate for the implementation of Adult Education Programme. Most facilitators in literacy centres have been teaching without the ICT devices. This present finding is in consonance with the findings of Adeyemo, Adedola & Adedola (2012) who concluded that there is lack of adequate and appropriate ICT devices for effective teaching in literacy centres.

The study also revealed that the extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State was low. This finding might be due to non-availability or low availability of ICT devices in most of our adult literacy centres. This implies that the ICT devices not available could not be utilized by adult educators. This finding agreed with the conclusion of Fasakun (2006) and Nwabuko (2004) who concluded that the lack of ICT devices in our literacy centres have constituted a cog in the wheel of adequate implementation of the Adult education programmes.

The study also revealed that the challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class are: inadequate ICT devices; irregular electricity hampering the utilization of available ICT tools for learning; lack of ready access to internet; lack of required technical support; and shortage of facilitators in the appropriate use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning process in the literacy centre. All these challenges pose a threat to the effective utilization of ICT to mediate teaching and learning process in adult literacy programmes.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that level of availability and extent of utilization of ICT devices in literacy centres in Ekiti State were low. The challenges faced using ICT tools for learning in the literacy class are inadequate ICT devices; irregular electricity hampering the utilization of available ICT tools for learning; lack of ready access to internet; lack of required technical support; and shortage of facilitators in the appropriate use of ICT to enhance teaching and learning process in the literacy centre.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government should equip adult literacy centres with adequate ICT devices
2. Facilitators of adult programme should endeavour to incorporate and prioritise the use of ICT in teaching and learning process.
3. Government should enforce the use of ICT devices in literacy centres as ICT use have the potentials to elicit and sustain adult learners' interest in literacy programmes and thus reduce the level of drop-out usually witnessed in adult literacy programme
4. Government and facilitators should work with every sense of purpose to reduce the challenges faced using these ICT devices in adult literacy programmes

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